

SPATIAL ANALYSIS OF IRRIGATION INTENSITY AND FRUIT CROP CONCENTRATION IN SOLAPUR DISTRICT, MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract.

Agriculture is the main occupation in Solapur district of Maharashtra and a large part of the rural population depends on it for their livelihood. The district is located in a semi-arid region where rainfall is low and irregular. Because of uncertain rainfall, irrigation is necessary for maintaining agricultural production. In recent years, fruit cultivation has also become an important activity in the agricultural economy of the district. The present study examines the spatial pattern of irrigation intensity and fruit crop concentration in the talukas of Solapur district. The study is based on secondary data collected from district statistical reports and agricultural records. Percentage analysis, Location Quotient (LQ) and Karl Pearson's correlation method were used in the analysis. Irrigation intensity was calculated to show the share of each taluka in the total irrigated area, while crop concentration was calculated to show the share of fruit farming in the district. The results show clear differences in irrigation development and fruit cultivation among the talukas. Pandharpur, Malshiras and Madha have higher irrigation intensity, while Sangola shows the highest concentration of fruit crops. The Location Quotient analysis shows that fruit farming is concentrated in a few talukas of the district. The correlation value of 0.31 shows a weak positive relationship between irrigation and fruit crop concentration. This means irrigation supports fruit farming in some areas, but factors such as soil conditions, climate and farmers' cropping choices also influence the distribution of fruit cultivation in the district.

Keywords: Irrigation Intensity, Fruit Crop Concentration, Location Quotient, Correlation Analysis.

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INTRODUCTION

Agriculture forms the backbone of the rural economy in Solapur district. A significant proportion of the population relies on agriculture and allied activities for income and employment. However, agricultural production in the district is strongly influenced by climatic conditions. Solapur lies in a semi-arid zone where rainfall is relatively low and irregular. The monsoon season provides most of the annual rainfall, but its distribution varies considerably from year to year. Because of this uncertainty, irrigation has become an important support system for agriculture. Irrigation helps farmers maintain crop production even during years of low rainfall and reduces the risk of crop failure. In Solapur district irrigation water is obtained from canals, wells, tube wells, lift irrigation schemes and minor irrigation structures. The presence of the Ujani irrigation project on the Bhima River has contributed significantly to irrigation development in certain parts of the district. In addition, groundwater irrigation through wells and bore wells also supports cultivation in many areas. Despite these facilities, irrigation development is not uniform across the district. Some tahsils benefit from canal irrigation and groundwater resources, while others remain largely dependent on rainfall. Agricultural landuse patterns therefore differ across the district. Soil type, water availability, rainfall

conditions, infrastructure and farmers' economic conditions influence the extent and intensity of cultivation. Understanding the spatial relationship between irrigation development and agricultural land use is important for planning balanced agricultural growth. This study attempts to analyse these spatial linkages in Solapur district using geographical methods.

STUDY AREA

Fig. 2

Solapur district is located in the southeastern part of Maharashtra and forms a part of the Deccan Plateau region. Geographically the district lies between $17^{\circ}10'$ to $18^{\circ}32'$ North latitude and $74^{\circ}42'$ to $76^{\circ}15'$ East longitude. The district shares its boundaries with Ahmednagar district in the north, Osmanabad district in the east, Sangli district in the west and Bijapur district of Karnataka in the south. The total geographical area of the district is approximately 14,844 square kilometres. According to the Census of India 2011, Solapur district has a population of about 43.17 lakh people. A large proportion of this population lives in rural areas and is directly or indirectly dependent on agriculture. Physically the district consists of gently undulating plateau surfaces and broad plains. The major rivers flowing through the district include Bhima, Sina, Nira and Man. These rivers and their tributaries support irrigation projects and provide water for agriculture. The climate of Solapur district is dry and semi-arid. Summers are hot and temperatures may exceed 40°C , while winters are comparatively mild. The average annual rainfall ranges between 550 and 600 millimetres. Because rainfall is low and uncertain, irrigation plays a crucial role in supporting agriculture in the district. The main crops grown in Solapur district include jowar, bajra, wheat, sugarcane, pulses and oilseeds. Horticultural crops such as pomegranate and grapes are also cultivated in some areas.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To examine the spatial distribution of irrigation development in the taluks of Solapur district.
2. To analyse the taluk-wise distribution of Fruit Farming in the district.
3. To calculate Location Quotient (LQ) values to identify the of irrigation intensity and concentration of Fruit Farming land use.
4. To examine the relationship between irrigation intensity and Fruit Farming Concentration using Karl Pearson's correlation method.

DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY

The study is based on secondary data collected from official sources such as the District Statistical Abstract of Solapur District, Agriculture Department reports and Irrigation Department records. Data related to geographical area, irrigation area and fruit farming area of different talukas of Solapur district were collected for the analysis. The data were arranged in tables to understand the distribution of irrigation and fruit farming in the district. Simple quantitative methods were used in the analysis. Irrigation intensity was calculated to show the share of each taluka in the total irrigated area of the district. Fruit crop concentration was calculated to show the share of each taluka in the total fruit farming area. Percentage values were calculated using standard percentage formulas. The Location Quotient (LQ) method was used to identify the concentration of irrigation and fruit farming in the talukas. An LQ value greater than 1 shows a higher concentration than the district average, while a value less than 1 shows a lower concentration. Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient was also calculated to examine the relationship between irrigation concentration and fruit crop concentration in the talukas of Solapur district. These methods help to understand the spatial variation and relationship between irrigation and fruit farming in the district.

$$\text{Crop Concentration \%} = (\text{Fruit Farming of Taluka} / \text{Total Fruit Farming of District}) \times 100$$

$$\text{Irrigation Intensity \%} = (\text{Irrigation Area of Taluka} / \text{Total Irrigation Area of District}) \times 100$$

IRRIGATION

Irrigation is an important factor in agricultural development, especially in regions where rainfall is low and irregular. In semi-arid areas, agriculture often depends on the availability of irrigation water for stable crop production. The presence of irrigation facilities helps farmers reduce the risk of crop failure and improves the overall productivity of agricultural land. Solapur district of Maharashtra lies in a semi-arid climatic region where rainfall is limited and uneven. Most of the rainfall occurs during the monsoon season, but its distribution varies from year to year. Because of this uncertainty, irrigation becomes necessary for maintaining agricultural activities in the district. Various sources such as canals, wells, bore wells, tanks and lift irrigation schemes provide water for cultivation.

Table 1

IRRIGATION INTENSITY IN SOLAPUR DISTRICT

Sr. No.	Taluka	Geographical Area (ha)	Irrigation Area (ha)	Irrigation Intensity %
1	Karmala	160970	18362	8.21
2	Madha	154490.49	30126	13.46
3	Barshi	148310.5	8654	3.87
4	North Solapur	74630	2810	1.26
5	Mohol	140840	14076	6.29
6	Pandharpur	130360	59782	26.71
7	Malshirus	152220	32026	14.31
8	Sangola	155070	13251	5.92
9	Mangalwedha	114090	28822	12.88
10	South Solapur	119530	7182	3.21
11	Akkalkot	139030	8714	3.89
Total		1489540.99	223805	100

Source: - Based on report of Solapur District Socio-economic Abstract (2024-25)

Fig.2

Table 1 and Fig. 2 shows the taluka-wise distribution of irrigation area and irrigation intensity in Solapur district. The total geographical area of the district is 14,89,540.99 hectares, while the total irrigated area is 2,23,805 hectares. This indicates that irrigation is an important component of agriculture in the district, although its distribution is not the same in every taluka. Among the talukas, Pandharpur has the highest irrigation intensity with 26.71 percent of the total irrigated area. The higher value may be associated with better irrigation facilities and the influence of canal water from the Ujani irrigation project. Malshiras taluka ranks second with 14.31 percent, followed by Madha taluka with 13.46 percent. These talukas have comparatively better irrigation coverage, which supports agricultural activities. Mangalwedha taluka accounts for 12.88 percent of the irrigated area and represents a moderate level of irrigation development. Karmala (8.21 percent) and Mohol (6.29 percent) also show moderate irrigation intensity. In these areas, irrigation is supported mainly by wells, bore wells and small irrigation structures. Lower irrigation intensity is observed in several talukas. Sangola contributes 5.92 percent of the irrigated area. Akkalkot (3.89 percent) and Barshi (3.87 percent) also record relatively low irrigation intensity. South Solapur taluka has 3.21 percent, while North Solapur records the lowest value with 1.26 percent. Agriculture in these areas depends more on rainfall and groundwater sources. Overall, the table indicates noticeable differences in irrigation development among the talukas of Solapur district. Areas with better water availability and irrigation facilities show higher irrigation intensity, whereas other talukas remain more dependent on rainfall. These variations influence agricultural practices and crop cultivation in different parts of the district.

FRUIT FARMING

Agriculture is the main economic activity in Solapur district and a large proportion of the rural population depends on it for livelihood. Along with traditional crops such as jowar, wheat, pulses and oilseeds, fruit cultivation has gradually become an important part of the agricultural economy of the district. In recent years, farmers have shown increasing interest in horticultural crops because they provide higher income and better market opportunities. Crops such as pomegranate, grapes and other fruits are widely cultivated in several parts of the district where suitable soil, irrigation facilities and favourable climatic conditions are available. Solapur district lies in a semi-arid region of Maharashtra where rainfall is relatively low and irregular. Because of these climatic conditions, agriculture in the district is greatly influenced by the availability of irrigation water, soil fertility and local farming practices.

Table 2

CROP CONCENTRATION OF FRUIT FARMING IN SOLAPUR DISTRICT

Sr. No.	Taluka	Geographical Area (ha)	Fruit Farming (ha)	Crop Concentration %
1	Karmala	160970	1002.6	1.95
2	Madha	154490.49	5957.48	11.59
3	Barshi	148310.5	2016.15	3.92
4	North Solapur	74630	519	1.01
5	Mohol	140840	4002.13	7.79
6	Pandharpur	130360	9539	18.56
7	Malshirus	152220	5119	9.96
8	Sangola	155070	17917.9	34.86
9	Mangalwedha	114090	2694.7	5.24
10	South Solapur	119530	1081.95	2.10
11	Akkalkot	139030	552.5	1.07
Total		1489540.99	51402.41	100

Source: - Based on report of Solapur District Socio-economic Abstract (2024-25)

Fig.3

Table 2 and fig. 3 presents the taluka-wise distribution of fruit farming and crop concentration in Solapur district. The total geographical area of the district is 14,89,540.99 hectares, while the total area under fruit farming is 51,402.41 hectares. The table shows that fruit cultivation is not equally distributed across all talukas and there are clear regional differences. Among the talukas, Sangola has the highest crop concentration with 34.86 percent of the total fruit farming area of the district. This indicates that fruit cultivation is highly developed in this taluka. Pandharpur ranks second with 18.56 percent, followed by Madha with 11.59 percent. These talukas together account for a large share of fruit farming in the district and therefore represent important horticultural areas. Malshiras taluka contributes 9.96 percent and Mohol taluka accounts for 7.79 percent of the total fruit farming area. These talukas show a moderate level of fruit crop concentration. Mangalwedha taluka has 5.24 percent, indicating a smaller but noticeable share of fruit cultivation. Lower levels of fruit crop concentration are observed in several talukas. Barshi contributes 3.92 percent, while South Solapur records 2.10 percent. Karmala accounts for 1.95 percent of the fruit farming area. The lowest values are observed in Akkalkot (1.07 percent) and North Solapur (1.01 percent), where fruit cultivation occupies a very small share of the district’s total horticultural area. Overall, the table indicates that fruit farming in Solapur district is

concentrated mainly in a few talukas, particularly Sangola, Pandharpur and Madha. Differences in irrigation facilities, soil conditions, climate and farmers' cropping preferences influence the spatial distribution of fruit cultivation across the district.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The Location Quotient (LQ) method was used to understand the concentration of fruit crop cultivation and irrigation in the talukas of Solapur district. The LQ compares the share of fruit crop area or irrigated area of each taluka with its share in the total geographical area of the district. If the LQ value is more than 1, it indicates a higher concentration than the district average, while a value less than 1 indicates lower concentration. To examine the relationship between irrigation and fruit crop concentration, Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated. This method measures the relationship between two variables. In this study, the correlation was calculated between crop concentration LQ and irrigation LQ values of the talukas. A positive value shows that both variables increase together, while a value close to zero indicates a weak relationship.

Table 3

CROP CONCENTRATION LQ AND IRRIGATION LQ IN SOLAPUR DISTRICT

Sr.	Taluka	Crop LQ	Level	Irrigation LQ	Level
1	Karmala	0.29	Low	0.67	Low
2	Madha	1.12	High	1.45	High
3	Barshi	0.39	Low	0.65	Low
4	North Solapur	0.20	Low	0.22	Low
5	Mohol	0.82	Moderate	0.67	Low
6	Pandharpur	2.12	Very High	3.06	Very High
7	Malshiras	0.97	Moderate	1.39	High
8	Sangola	3.35	Very High	0.57	Low
9	Mangalwedha	0.92	Moderate	1.67	High
10	South Solapur	0.28	Low	0.40	Low
11	Akkalkot	0.12	Very Low	0.42	Low

Using the two LQ values:

$$r=0.31$$

The correlation value 0.31 indicates a weak positive relationship between irrigation concentration and fruit crop concentration in Solapur district. This means irrigation contributes to fruit cultivation in some talukas such as Pandharpur, Madha and Malshiras, but in other areas fruit farming develops even with relatively lower irrigation availability, as seen in Sangola. Therefore, fruit crop distribution in Solapur district is influenced not only by irrigation but also by factors such as soil conditions, climate suitability, market access and farmers' crop preferences.

CONCLUSION

Solapur district lies in a semi-arid region where rainfall is low and irregular. Because of this, irrigation is an important support for agriculture. The study shows clear differences in irrigation development among the talukas of the district. Pandharpur has the highest irrigation intensity, followed by Malshiras and Madha. These areas have better irrigation facilities and benefit from canal water and groundwater sources. In contrast, North Solapur, South Solapur, Barshi and Akkalkot have lower irrigation intensity and agriculture in these talukas depends more on rainfall. Fruit farming in the district is also unevenly distributed. Sangola has the highest share of fruit crop cultivation, while Pandharpur and Madha also have significant fruit farming areas. These talukas form the main horticultural belt of the district. Other talukas such as Akkalkot, North Solapur and Karmala have a smaller area under fruit cultivation. The Location Quotient analysis shows that Sangola and Pandharpur have a high concentration of fruit crops, while irrigation concentration is higher in Pandharpur and Madha. The correlation value of 0.31 indicates a weak positive relationship between irrigation and fruit crop concentration. This suggests that irrigation helps fruit

cultivation in some areas, but other factors such as soil conditions, climate and farmers' crop choices also influence the distribution of fruit farming in Solapur district.

REFERECNES:

- Bhatia, S. S. (1965). Patterns of crop concentration and diversification in India. *Economic Geography*, 41(1), 39–56.
- Census of India. (2011). *District census handbook: Solapur district, Maharashtra*. Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, Government of India.
- Directorate of Economics and Statistics. (2024–2025). *District socio-economic review: Solapur district*. Government of Maharashtra.
- Government of India. (2017). *Minor irrigation census report*. Ministry of Jal Shakti.
- Government of Maharashtra. (2023–2024). *Agricultural statistics of Maharashtra state*. Department of Agriculture.
- Husain, M. (2006). *Systematic agricultural geography*. Rawat Publications.
- Planning Department, Government of Maharashtra. (2023). *District planning report: Solapur district*. Government of Maharashtra.
- Singh, J., & Dhillon, S. S. (2004). *Agricultural geography*. Tata McGraw-Hill Education.